

EDITORIAL

Setting the standard: my vision for a reliable, authoritative, and accessible journal for the medical and biomedical sciences

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Abstract: Scientific communication faces growing challenges in maintaining credibility, as the manipulation of information has become easier than ever before. Predatory journals proliferate, paper mills exploit advances in artificial intelligence in order to fabricate data and manuscripts, and qualified scientists are increasingly unwilling to serve as reviewers. This editorial introduces *Acta Studiorum Medicorum et Biomedicorum* by outlining its broad scope, its diverse article types, and its thematic priorities. More importantly, it conveys the editor's vision for its gradual development into a reliable, authoritative, and accessible journal that serves the medical and biomedical sciences. A key objective of this newly-launched journal is to remove barriers in academic publishing by fostering scholarly dialogue through a unique variety of article types (many of which are rarely accommodated by other journals in the field) and by welcoming manuscripts (co-)authored by undergraduate and postgraduate students. Moreover, by championing open science, the journal aims at serving as a platform where emerging and established scholars can engage with and uphold the rigorous standards of scientific communication. Recognizing the responsibility of gatekeeping scientific credibility, the editor pledges to safeguard the integrity of the journal's peer review process; the latter is ambitiously warranted to be timely, thorough, and constructive, conducted exclusively by qualified experts. Additionally, by adhering to the highest editorial standards, the editorial board is expected to guarantee consistency, quality, and

reliability in the journal's published content. Finally, the journal's publisher has committed to facilitating article publication in this year's issues with the waiving of the processing fees, thereby allowing for the editorial board to set the standard for the journal's content. In these challenging times, *Acta Studiorum Medicorum et Biomedicorum* is not launched as just another open-access journal, but as a deliberate effort to address some of the pressing challenges facing scientific publishing today.

Keywords: accessibility; credibility; editorial priorities; peer review; scientific misconduct

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A letter authored by Jaime A. Teixeira da Silva and published in *Philosophia* a couple of years ago (Teixeira da Silva, 2023) makes for a very interesting reading on how "junk science", "junk journals", and "junk publishing management" pose a fundamental risk not only to the credibility of science, but also to 'the entire fabric of society that relies on science-based decisions'. Although I do not entirely agree with some of the author's pessimistic assessments, Teixeira da Silva (2023) makes particularly insightful remarks on the practical consequences of the adoption and use of the so-called "junk science" as reliable, especially in an era in which the manipulation of information is easier than ever before. In my view, the problem of "junk science" must be ad-

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Table 1. Outline of the thematic priorities of *Acta Studiorum Medicorum et Biomedicorum*, as defined by its founding editorial board (2025).

Thematic priorities	Description
clinical research	manuscripts communicating diagnostic or therapeutic advancements
experimental research	manuscripts describing the findings of studies enriching our understanding of the mechanisms of disease and / or attempting to test potential cures
translational medical research	manuscripts communicating research findings that bridge experimental research discoveries and clinical applications
public health and healthcare policy	manuscripts focusing on population health, disease prevention, drug safety, or healthcare policies
innovative techniques and technologies	manuscripts presenting the development and assessment of novel methods and tools in medicine and biomedicine
health inequalities	manuscripts addressing health inequalities at a local, national, or international level
emerging topics	manuscripts offering balanced insights into recent developments and challenges in medicine and biomedicine

dressed at two (not entirely independent) levels: that of the responsibility for scientific misconduct and that of the gatekeeping of scientific credibility.

The responsibility for scientific misconduct weights heavily on the researchers themselves, their research supervisors and / or mentors, and their institutions (Zhaksylyk *et al.*, 2023), while the adoption of enhanced peer review practices (Forero *et al.*, 2025), the early (and formal) training on how to conduct a peer review (Hesselberg *et al.*, 2023), and the restraining of predatory publishing (Laine *et al.*, 2025) can also play a small role in discouraging scientific misconduct. On the other hand, the gatekeeping of scientific credibility remains a responsibility largely shared between authors (including, in most cases, their institutions), reviewers, editors, and publishers (Kretser *et al.*, 2019). These responsibilities are unlikely to be significantly reallocated in the forthcoming years.

What has changed over the last few years is the availability of credible and knowledgeable reviewers (who increasingly have no time or interest to accommodate the increasing number of requests for their uncompensated services) and the release of generative artificial intelligence (AI) in the form of user-friendly large language models (LLMs). Although LLMs have the capacity to significantly strengthen the quality of the peer review process (Lee *et al.*, 2025), they have already delivered a blow to scientific integrity through their misuse by authors and paper mills. Paper mills, in particular, have mastered the use of AI: they use it to write manuscripts faster and then sell the authorship to clients (Dadkhah *et al.*, 2023). Unsurprisingly, fake papers published as a result of this process can more easily be published in predatory and hijacked journals, although reputable journals have also been found to publish such papers, mainly after what is suspected to be peer review manipulation (Dadkhah *et al.*, 2023). Dadkhah *et al.* (2023) have suggested a method for detecting fake manuscripts / papers, which is undoubtedly thorough and could be particularly useful to readers,

reviewers, editors, and publishers; however, one should keep in mind that, as time passes, the further AI development and refinement will very likely render such methods less sensitive.

In these challenging times, *Acta Studiorum Medicorum et Biomedicorum* is launched as an open-access, peer-reviewed journal aiming to serve the wider and established medical and biomedical disciplines in a reliable and authoritative manner. With the support of a small editorial board of experienced and accomplished physicians and bioscientists, the journal will be published semiannually and will be considering well-written manuscripts that convey reliable and previously unpublished data or offer balanced insight into recent developments in the aforementioned disciplines. My vision for *Acta Studiorum Medicorum et Biomedicorum* is to establish it as a journal that embraces two fundamental priorities: (i) the fostering of scholarly dialogue through a unique variety of article types (many of which are rarely accommodated by other peer-reviewed journals in the field) and (ii) the welcoming of manuscripts (co-)authored by undergraduate and postgraduate students. By setting these two fundamental priorities, I aim at positioning the journal at the forefront of the broader movement advocating for open science, thereby establishing it as an accessible platform for emerging and established scholars to engage with and uphold the rigorous standards that define scientific communication. In doing so, the journal aspires to bridge gaps in academic publishing, to encourage meaningful discourse, and to empower the next generation of medical and biomedical professionals.

As editor, I acknowledge my profound responsibility in safeguarding the scientific credibility of this journal's content. This duty extends beyond my professional standing and reputation; it directly impacts the integrity of the journal, the trust placed in us by authors, as well as the fair and constructive evaluation of their work. Alongside the esteemed members of the editorial board, I am committed to ensuring that all manuscripts

undergo rigorous assessment and, if accepted, that they are published promptly and accessibly. Given the journal's focus, this responsibility carries significant implications for clinical practice and patient care. To this end, I will implement systematic measures to not only preserve the integrity of the peer review process, but to also ensure that the latter is consistently conducted in a timely, thorough, and constructive manner by appropriately-qualified experts (Glonti *et al.*, 2019). This commitment will be actively supported and closely monitored by the journal's editorial board members, thereby reinforcing our dedication to excellence and transparency.

Finally, the journal's publisher has committed to facilitating article publication in this year's issues with the waiving of the processing fees, thereby allowing for the editorial board to set the standard for the journal's content. Therefore, I hereby encourage readers to take advantage of the waived article processing charges for all manuscripts submitted for publication to this journal within 2025, I invite submissions that align well with the thematic priorities outlined in Table 1, and I assure all interested parties that the journal will uphold the highest editorial standards (as these are continuously refined and strengthened) in order to ensure consistency, high quality, and reliability in its published content (Gasparyan *et al.*, 2018).

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Conflicts of interest statement

The author of this editorial (AZ) serves as the editor of the journal and holds a majority ownership stake in its publisher (St Cuthbert Press Ltd).

Data availability statement

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